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Challenges of Local People's Participation in Ward Shava and Open Budget Session: A Case Study on Different Union Parishads at Trishal Upazila

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Abstract

The active involvement of people is of paramount importance in establishing a robust governance framework in Bangladesh. By means of active citizen engagement, individuals have the opportunity to share their perspectives on the process of governmental decision-making. From this perspective, this study investigates the impediments to active community involvement in Ward Shava and Open Budget Sessions within various Union Parishads in Trishal Upazila. The study was conducted based on a quantitative approach. A total of 300 local residents from different Union Parishads (Amirabari, Bailar, Baliparar, Dhanikhola, Mathbari, Rampura, Sakhua, and Trishal) under Trishal Upazila participated in the cross-sectional survey. The findings of the study reveal that a significant majority, i.e., 80% and 83% of the respondents, did not actively engage in this initial and final phase of the budgeting process, respectively, whereas only 39% of individuals residing in rural areas actively engaged in the Ward Shava. The results also show that a number of related factors, such as low levels of awareness, low rates of literacy among rural populations, political influence, intimidation and fear, distrust, bureaucratic complexity, etc., significantly impede people's participation in Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings. In this vein, addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to raise awareness through community education, capacity building, and inclusive decision-making, promote accountability and transparency, and establish effective communication between local authorities and the community. However, the study findings incorporate both theoretical and practical contribution in the field of local government.

Key Words: People's Participation, Ward Shava, Open Budget Meeting, Local Government, Union Parishads, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Participation often pertains to individuals' active involvement in the decision-making process concerning the equitable distribution of development program benefits, as well as their engagement in endeavors aimed at evaluating these programs (Fitzgerald et al. 2016). In each democratic country, people's participation is crucial because it affects people's living standards and governance systems (Begum and Ahmed 2023). In that case, decentralization is often associated with many apparent advantages, including enhanced accessibility to decision makers, increased engagement of diverse social groups in the decision-making process, and heightened responsibility among decision makers (Andersson, Gibson, and Lehoucq 2004). Decentralization entails the direct empowerment of local individuals, whereby the involvement of local residents, including civil society, is solicited in the process of formulating and executing governmental decisions (Uddin 2016). People's participation in decentralized governance is seen as a dynamic procedure by which individuals exert influence on the trajectory and execution of a development initiative with the objective of safeguarding their welfare in relation to sustainable national development (Denhardt et al. 2009).

However, people can participate in the governmental decision-making process in Bangladesh since a parliamentary system governs the country and authority is somewhat delegated to local government entities. Since the local government institutions in Bangladesh practice the participatory governance approach, it provides substantial benefits to its citizens and empowers local government officials to develop independent decisions (Uddin 2019). The Union Parishad (UP) functions as a local government unit that facilitates the active participation of all citizens in decision-making processes. The promotion of people's participation facilitates enhanced service delivery and the implementation of sustainable choices (Hamilton 2013). Nevertheless, there exist several formal mechanisms (avenues) aimed at facilitating general people's participation in the Union Parishad. These mechanisms encompass open budget sessions, which encompass both preliminary and final budget meetings; the Ward Shaba, comprising the electorate of each ward; the village court, consisting of a chairman and four

members; standing committees that address specific functional matters; local elections held on a quinquennial basis; and the provision of access to information, thereby granting individuals the right to obtain relevant information (Uddin 2019).

In the past decade, much research has focused on people's participation and its challenges for the local government system around the globe. Ahmed et al. (2022) conducted a study on the modern practices of people's participation in different avenues of rural local government. The research largely focused on the most recent developments in people's engagement in several local government avenues. According to the study findings, participation in Union Parishads is functional because decentralization makes it easier to transfer power from the national to the local level, but most rural residents find it extremely difficult to engage in the various Union Parishad activities because of political complexities, institutional corruption, inadequate education, and general ignorance (Tanjil Ahmed, Azizur Rahman, and Tamanna Akter 2022). In another study, Ahmed and Akter (2022) articulate that the majority of rural residents were unaware of the Union Parishad Act, open budget meetings, and the UP-standing committee. The study also demonstrates that a significant portion of rural residents did not take part in the Ward Shaba and UP standing committees, the final open budget session, or the pre-open budget session (Ahmed and Akter 2022). In a similar vein, Uddin (2019) asserts that local people are empowered in Bangladesh as a result of their engagement in the local government institution, i.e., Union Parishad. The study's results indicate that the participation of community members in local government institutions serves as both an opportunity and a means for their empowerment. Despite the fact that many rural people expressed their opinion at the different avenues in rural local government (like Union Parishad), the engagement status of individuals in Union Parishad was very disheartening, as a significant number of members were unaware of their rights, illiterate, and could not get sufficient opportunities to engage (Uddin 2019).

The rationale for the people's participation in different avenues in Union Parishads (UPs) is the expectation that local people would actively interact with UPs to address and resolve issues pertaining to their livelihoods. Additionally, these mechanisms provide a

platform for negotiation between the local population and UP officials. Simultaneously, it is expected that the elected representatives possess the capacity to discern their respective domains of priority requirements and ensure collaborative efforts to address the needs of local people. However, among the different avenues of people's participation in the Union Parishad, Ward Shava and open budget session is very crucial since most of the local people share their thought on these two platforms (Ahmed 2023). Nevertheless, several challenges have been observed regarding people's participation in the different avenues of Union Parishad. The impartiality of decision-making based on people's participation is influenced by political pressures, poor communication and bureaucratic complexity. Addressing these challenges is vital for promoting genuine and diverse participation of local people in Union Parishad activities and fostering democratic local governance. Therefore, researchers contemplate that people's participation in the decision-making process and incorporation of stakeholders would help to strengthen accountability, transparency, administrative efficiency, improve citizen awareness, etc. regarding ensuring democratic governance in Bangladesh.

1.1 Executive Summary

A balanced socioeconomic development at the local level in Bangladesh depends heavily on people's participation in the government decision-making process. In spite of this fact, there are still many challenges and facets associated with getting people involved in local governing processes. In many cases, rural people, marginalized communities, women, and individuals with lower socioeconomic status find it difficult to voice their concerns or opinions during the Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings due to societal hierarchies and prevailing norms. In this context, the study aims to investigate the challenges surrounding people's participation in Ward Shava (community meetings) and Open Budget Meetings within the context of different Union Parishads (rural local administrative units) in Trishal Upazila. The study has been conducted using a quantitative approach. The findings of the study predominantly highlight the associated challenges (such as poor access to information, poor literacy rate, poor awareness, inadequate infrastructure and resources, bureaucratic complexity, political

influence, intimidation and fear, etc.) of people's participation at Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings that hinder concrete rural local development. The implications of these findings are significant. To enhance grassroots democracy, it is imperative to implement targeted awareness campaigns, improving citizens' understanding of the importance of these sessions. Transparency reforms within Union Parishads are necessary to build trust, and more open communication channels must be established to foster active participation. However, addressing these challenges would empower local communities to actively engage in democratic processes and contribute to more inclusive and effective decision-making at the grassroots level.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The active participation of people in local governance processes is crucial for fostering democratic practices and ensuring transparent decision-making. In recent years, the concept of participatory democracy has gained prominence, emphasizing the involvement of citizens in decision-making at the grassroots level. Despite the recognition of its importance, people's participation in local governance processes remains a complex and multifaceted challenge. One of the central issues pertains to the accessibility of information and awareness about the meetings themselves. Often, citizens are unaware of the timing, agenda, and purpose of these meetings, leading to limited attendance and engagement. Additionally, elements like socioeconomic disparities and power dynamics undermine the effectiveness of people's participation. This results in an imbalanced representation of the community's needs and preferences, undermining the principle of inclusivity that underpins participatory democracy. These knowledge gap can lead to passive participation or disinterest among attendees, ultimately limiting the potential of these meetings to contribute to informed decision-making. Moreover, bureaucratic obstacles and a lack of accountability mechanisms may hinder the effectiveness of Ward Shava and open budget meetings. Therefore, this study aims to explore these challenges in the specific context of different Union Parishads in Trishal Upazila. By understanding the nuances of these challenges, policymakers, local authorities, and civil society organizations can develop tailored strategies to enhance people's participation in these crucial local governance mechanisms.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The findings of the study incorporate both theoretical and practical contributions. It investigates the socio-economic, cultural, and political factors that impact people's ability to contribute meaningfully to discussions regarding local development plans and budget allocations. By examining the challenges faced by local residents in these participatory processes, the study provides insights into the broader issues of community engagement, transparency, and accountability in local governance. In particular, the researchers analyze the various factors that lead to the limited participation of local people in Ward Shava and Open Budget Meetings. Moreover, the study explores the influence of gender, socioeconomic status, and social norms on individuals' involvement in the decision-making process. Practically, the significance of this study lies in its potential to inform policymakers and local authorities about the existing gaps in citizen participation in Ward Shava and Open Budget Meetings and offer recommendations to enhance the inclusivity and effectiveness of these democratic mechanisms. Theoretically, by identifying barriers, suggesting strategies to overcome them, and developing existing knowledge on that particular issue, the research contributes to the overall goal of strengthening grassroots democracy and fostering more transparent and responsive governance at the local level in Bangladesh.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The principal aim of this study is to explore the associated challenges of local people's participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Session in the selected UPs in Trishal Upazila Parishad.

The specific objectives are

- a) To identify the challenges of people's participation in Ward Shava in the selected UPs in Trishal Upazila Parishad.
- b) To investigate the challenges of people's participation in Open Budget Session in the selected UPs in Trishal Upazila Parishad.
- c) To recommend ways for addressing the challenges of people's participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Session in the selected UPs in Trishal Upazila Parishad.

2. Methodology

This study is exploratory in nature. In this particular setting, based on the positivism philosophy, a quantitative methodology has been used to perform the research. The data from the survey has been gathered using a quantitative technique. The primary justification for using a quantitative technique is that it yields data that can be numerically stated, allowing the researcher to use statistical tests to prepare assertions based on the data. In addition, the quantitative method is significant since it facilitates the preparation of descriptive statistics (Demetrius Madrigal 2020). However, the survey data was gathered from the local population in Bangladesh who are members of the selected Union Parishads (i.e., Amirabari, Bailar, Baliparar, Dhanikhola, Mathbari, Rampura, Sakhua, and Trishal) in Trishal Upazila. The survey comprised 300 participants in total, drawn from five Union Parishads of Trishal Upazilla. Additionally, data was gathered from a randomly chosen sample using standardized questionnaires. The purpose of the survey was to gather pertinent demographic data as well as particulars about general people's involvement in Ward Shava and open budget sessions, such as how often they attend, what obstacles they face, and how beneficial they believe the sessions to be. Finally, SPSS and MS Excel were used to analyze the data. Correspondingly, all ethical considerations have been closely adhered to in order to guarantee the balance between the potential risks associated with research and its potential benefits.

3. Findings of the Study

On the basis of a cross-sectional survey, this section significantly illustrates the challenges of local people's participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Session in the selected UPs in Trishal Upazila Parishad. This research presents and analyzes data using univariate analysis. Bar charts and pie charts were used in this presentation to display the essential facts. Predominantly, percentage analysis and frequency distribution have been applied to present the data.

3.1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

Since demographic information reflects the general position and circumstances of the participants, it is regarded as crucial information in any research.

Table 1: Demographic Analysis

Variables		Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Gender	Female	220	73.3	73.3
	Male	80	26.7	100.0
Age Range	21-30	56	18.7	18.7
	31-40	132	44.0	62.7
	41- Above	112	37.3	100.0
Education Level	Received Primary Education	92	30.7	30.7
	Received Higher Education	124	41.3	72.0
	Illiterate	84	28.0	100.0
Employment Status	Day Labor	64	21.3	21.3
	Businessmen	104	34.7	56.0
	Government Job Holder	36	12.0	68.0
	Private Job Holder	32	10.7	78.7
	Housewife	48	16.0	94.7
	Unemployed	16	5.3	100.0

[Source: Field Survey on Different Union Parishads under Trishal Upazila, Mymensingh, June 2022]

Table 1 illustrates the demographic information of the respondents including analyzing respondents' gender status, age range, education levels and profession. According to the survey, it was observed that 73.3% (N =220) of the respondents were male and 26.7% (N =80) of the respondents were female. This number in gender representation has a significant implication in the findings, as it suggests that the perspectives and experiences of men are more heavily represented in the results compared to women. Besides, the findings also reveal that 44% (N =132) of the respondents belonged to the age group 31–40, and 37.3% (N =112) of the respondents belonged to the age group 41 and above. These statistics indicate that the study primarily focuses on adults, particularly those in their

thirties and older who belonged to the rural areas of Bangladesh. Accordingly, the survey data reveals that 28% (N =84) of respondents were illiterate, 30.7% (N =92) had just a basic education, and 41.3% (N =124) of respondents had a high level of education.

These statistics suggest that a significant portion of the respondents have some level of education, with a substantial proportion having received higher education. The mentioned occupational diversity in Table 1 suggests that the study encompasses individuals from various walks of life and employment sectors. The inclusion of day laborers, housewives, private job holders, and government job holders adds valuable diversity to the sample, as their perspectives differ based on their respective roles and experiences.

3.2 Challenges of People's Participation in the Pre Open Budget Session and Final Budget Meeting

The study investigated the level of people's participation in the pre-open budget session and the final open budget session. According to the field survey, only 20% (N=60), and 17% (N=51) of rural people participated in the pre-open budget session and final budget meeting in the Union Parishads (See in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Challenges of People's Participation in the Pre Open Budget Session and Final Budget Meeting [Source: Field Survey on Different Union Parishads under Trishal Upazila, Mymensingh, June 2022]

These findings indicate that a significant majority, 80% (N=240), and 83% (N=249) did not actively engage in this initial and final phase of the budgeting process respectively. One possible

reason and challenge for the low participation rate is a lack of awareness among rural residents about the pre-open budget session and final budget meetings. The researchers observed that rural people are not informed about the significance of this session or how it can impact local development. Another challenge was that the session had not been inclusive enough, failing to involve a wide range of community members, especially marginalized groups. In such instances, the low participation rate among rural residents means that the budget-making process does not fully represent the needs and goals of the whole community. Furthermore, minimal participation raises questions regarding accountability and transparency in the distribution of public funds.

3.3 Challenges of People's Participation in Ward Shava

Figure 2: Challenges of People's Participation in Ward Shava [Source: Field Survey on Different Union Parishads under Trishal Upazila, Mymensingh, June 2022]

The study also investigated the level of people's participation in the Ward Shava. The findings of the field study indicate that a mere 39% (N=117) of individuals residing in rural areas actively engaged in the Ward Shava within the Union Parishads. This indicates that a substantial majority, up to 61% (N=183), did not actively participate in the Ward Shava, which serves as a crucial forum for decision-making at the community level. In that case, one significant challenge was how much rural residents recognize and comprehend the significance of Ward Shava in rural development. Moreover, the perception of whether participating in Ward Shava meetings can lead to tangible improvements in the community might influence

people's decisions to attend or not. However, the relatively low participation rate raises questions about whether the Ward Shava accurately represents the views and interests of the entire community.

3.4 Factors Associated with Major Challenges behind People's Participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Meetings

Regarding the factors associated with major challenges behind people's participation in Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings in Union Parishads, the survey findings shed light on several barriers that hinder people's participation at the local level of decision-making.

Figure 3: Factors Associated with Major Challenges behind People's Participation [Source: Field Survey on Different Union Parishads under Trishal Upazila, Mymensingh, June 2022]

One of the most prominent challenges identified in the survey is that 79% (N=237) of the respondents had limited information about the Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings. In that case, the lack of effective channels for disseminating information to the community, insufficient communication, and poor outreach efforts by local authorities to inform residents about these meetings were considered as key issues. Besides, a significant portion of respondents, 61% (N=183), had low literacy rates which impede their ability to understand complex budget documents and the purpose of the meetings. Moreover, a substantial majority, 72% (N= 216), reported facing political influence as a barrier to participation which indicates that political pressure or coercion to support specific agendas or candidates.

Similarly, the survey also revealed that a significant 76% (N=228) of respondents faced intimidation and fear when it came to attending Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings. This climate of fear deters community members from attending such meetings.

Conversely, a significant number of respondents (71%, N=213) cited timing and scheduling as issues affecting their participation. Most of the respondents argued that meetings scheduled at inconvenient times which creates conflict with work or family responsibilities. Moreover, 78%, (N=234) of respondents faced bureaucratic complexity which indicates the complex administrative processes that deter or delay participation. In this case, bureaucratic hurdles make it difficult to access information or engage with local government. Overall, the findings suggest that there are multifaceted challenges that deter people from participating in Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings.

3.5 Ways to Enhance People's Participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Meetings

Figure 4: Ways to Enhance People's Participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget Meetings

[Source: Field Survey on Different Union Parishads under Trishal Upazila, Mymensingh, June 2022]

The study also explored ways to enhance people's participation in Ward Shava and the Open Budget meetings. According to the survey, an overwhelming majority (82%, N=246) suggested that the awareness campaign would be the best measure to address issues related to people's participation. This awareness campaign may include informative workshops, seminars, and community meetings.

Besides, a significant 88% (N=264) of respondents emphasized community education that can enhance civic participation in the local decision-making process. Offering civic education programs to improve residents' understanding of local governance, budgeting, and decision-making processes; providing training on how to read and interpret budget documents; and encouraging critical thinking can boost the people's participation. As well, many respondents, (84%, N=252) recognized the importance of transparency and accountability in promoting participation. In this vein, making budget documents and decisions easily accessible to the public; regularly updating and sharing information on budget allocation, expenditures, and project progress; and creating mechanisms for residents to monitor and hold local authorities' accountability can be the best way to enhance local people's participation in the mentioned avenues.

An overwhelming 86% (N=258) of respondents suggested that flexible timing for meetings would encourage greater participation which emphasizes scheduling meetings at times that accommodate the diverse schedules and responsibilities of community members. Respectively, a substantial 81% (N=243) of respondents emphasized the importance of community feedback mechanisms.

Conversely, many respondents (77%, N=231) recognized the need for community capacity building. This can include training and support to community leaders and representatives on how to effectively engage with residents and facilitate productive meetings. A majority of respondents (68%, N=204) highlighted the importance of having conflict resolution mechanisms in place. This strategy can incorporate promoting open dialogue, a culture of respectful disagreement, and appointing impartial mediators to address disputes that arise during meetings. Correspondingly, 66% (N=198) of respondents emphasized the importance of inclusive decision-making processes. In this context, meetings should be inclusive and open to all community members, regardless of background or status, as well as actively seeking input from marginalized groups and underrepresented communities so that they can ensure their voices are heard.

4. Discussion of the Study

The study demonstrates the obstacles that hinder people's participation in the vital democratic processes of Ward Shava and Open Budget Sessions within the different Union Parishads in Trishal Upazila. Key findings highlight a fundamental lack of awareness and understanding among local residents about the significance of these sessions, a factor impeding their active participation. Bureaucratic hurdles and a lack of transparency within Union Parishads emerge as major barriers, eroding trust and discouraging community involvement. Besides, communication gaps between local authorities and residents further exacerbate the problem. Ahmed and Akter 2022; Uddin 2019; and Ahmed et al. 2022 supported these findings and articulated that rural local people are still struggling to ensure their participation in the different avenues of rural local government (Union Parishads). The implications of these findings are noteworthy. In this vein, implementing focused awareness efforts to increase residents' comprehension of the significance of these sessions (Ward Shava and Open Budget Meetings) is essential to strengthening grassroots democracy. In order to promote active engagement, more open lines of communication must be built, and transparency improvements within Union Parishads are also important to generate rural people's confidence. After all, addressing these challenges is vital to ensuring that the voices and concerns of local residents are integrated into decision-making processes at the union level. By addressing these obstacles and promoting inclusive participation, Trishal Upazila can move towards a more democratic and responsive governance structure that would truly represent its diverse community.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study highlights several significant insights regarding the difficulties faced by local people in participating effectively in Ward Shava and Open Budget Sessions within various Union Parishads in Trishal Upazila. Through a comprehensive discussion of the findings, it becomes evident that a range of factors hampers local people's participation in these crucial decision-making processes. Primarily, the research underscores the lack of awareness and information among the local population about the significance

of Ward Shava and Open Budget Sessions. This deficiency in understanding inhibits active involvement and engagement, hindering the democratic process at the grassroots level. Besides, the study demonstrates that due to several associated factors including political influence, intimidation and fear, lack of trust, inadequate resources and infrastructure, and inconvenient timing hinder the people's participation in the Ward Shava and Open Budget meetings to a greater extent. Furthermore, the study identifies bureaucratic hurdles and a lack of transparency within Union Parishads as substantial obstacles. These challenges create an environment of mistrust and apprehension, deterring residents from actively participating in these sessions. Moreover, the research highlights the importance of bridging the communication gap between local authorities and community members. Improved communication channels and platforms for dialogue can foster trust and encourage greater participation. To end, the research illuminates the multifaceted challenges that impede local people's participation in Ward Shava and Open Budget Sessions in Trishal Upazila. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to raise awareness, promote transparency, and establish effective communication between local authorities and the community. In particular, inclusive decision-making, conflict resolution mechanisms, community feedback mechanisms, community education, flexible timing of meetings, and rural people's capacity building could be effective measures to address the issues of people's participation in open budget meetings and Ward Shava in local government units in Bangladesh. Overcoming these hurdles is essential for fostering genuine grassroots democracy and ensuring that the voices and needs of local residents are heard and considered in decision-making processes at the union level.

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